

DIGITAL STORYTELLING: AGROFORESTRY PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

1. Bees in a beehive 2. Branded honey in a jar 3. Sugar Daddies entrepreneur in a forest 4. Bees and a beehive (Photos: Sugar Daddies Honey Company)

WHAT AND WHY

Storytelling is a marketing and branding method for disseminating information on products and services. Also, with storytelling policymakers and practitioners can encounter challenges to receive support for instance for proactive resilience planning and climate action. Whereas traditional storytelling has taken place in oral, verbal and visual forms through face-to-face communication or physical artefacts, digital storytelling can be done through audio, video, images and texts disseminated through technology. Storytelling done by individual agroforestry farms and enterprise builds not only brands of these individual farms and enterprises but also wider brand identity of agroforestry as a sector and different agroforestry systems, products and services in comparison to conventional systems. One example of how digital storytelling is used in the context of agroforestry systems is the Sugar Daddies Honey Company and its digital storytelling through turning negative rural storylines into attractive rural places.

Keywords: Marketing, branding, storytelling.

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

In general, digital storytelling consists of seven elements: perspective of the story and storyteller's relationship to the story, core question or "secret" which keeps audience engaged, emotional content that make audience to feel connection to the story, own personal unique tone of voice, music and soundscape which support the story, simplicity and economical use of material which is no more than what the story requires, and pace and rhythm of the story. The concept of turning negative rural storylines into attractive rural places (sexing up or glamorising rural places) consists of mixing story, history and locality with generational experience, rural and urban mix, and visual and aesthetic emphasis on clarity and minimalism in marketing and branding through giving emphasis to negative features associated with the countryside.

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ADVANTAGES

Storytelling is a universal way of communication. In essence, stories support understanding, remembering and identifying with what is in the story. Stories affect people's attitudes and are efficient tools for influencing people. Stories are made for specific audiences such as current or prospective customers of a farm or an enterprise.

Storytelling can have an important role in building up an image of agroforestry as consumers have, in general, very little information on agroforestry and its products and services, and benefits of agroforestry compared with conventional agricultural and forestry systems for consumers' decision-making purposes in Finland. Storytelling can support consumers to make informed decisions on consumption choices, to have deeper understanding on different food production options and their effects on environment, and to have more profound insight on countryside and its realities.

Stories and the capacity to utilise them are intangible capital, story capital, for advancing for instance marketing and branding, unique to each farm and enterprise. Storytelling can bring unique holistic experiences and meanings to customers as future vision stories, background stories of a farm or enterprise and its products and services, historical birth stories of the farm/enterprise, stories of services from the perspective of a consumer, customer stories of background and motivations, reference stories and value stories. Through turning negative rural storylines into attractive rural places by for instance using photos of old machinery, old buildings and reality of honey production work done in field, Sugar Daddies Honey company sells more than a product – they sell imaginaries, emotional connections to a place and feelings of belonging to a rural place.

Digital storytelling offers an opportunity to reach a wider consumer base than with traditional storytelling. In the context of agroforestry products and services, online presence in different online platforms may offer farmers a new and expanded client base that extends beyond the local rural area. Whereas in digital space competition can be fierce based on price, storytelling offers a possibility to differentiate from others. In the era of information overflow in digital space, storytelling supports conveying information in smaller pieces in more digestible format for consumers.

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HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Storytelling can have an important role in building up an image of agroforestry.**
- **Storytelling is a marketing and branding method for disseminating information on products and services.**
- **Digital storytelling offers an opportunity to possibly a much wider consumer base than traditional storytelling.**

Sugar Daddies entrepreneurs maintaining the beehives in a forest
(Photo: Sugar Daddies Honey Company)